

Contents

Contents	1
The file structure of RaVeN	2
Instruction for the experimental environment setup	3
System requirements	3
Caveats	3
Instructions for reproducing experiments	3
Untargeted UAP verification.....	3
Targeted UAP verification.....	3
Worst-case hamming distance verification.....	3
Monotonicity verification.....	3
Ablation w.r.t difference constraints.....	3
Designing custom tests	4

The file structure of RaVeN

We show the file structure of RaVeN code with directories shown in blue and the files are black with the major contributions shown in red.

Instruction for the experimental environment setup

We have an 'environment.yml' file which can be installed with 'conda env create -f environment.yml'. The code can then be run with a Gurobi license active. However, for ease of use, we also provide a VM with everything installed and set up, the VM can be installed by downloading the ova file, 'RaVeN-VM.ova'. For VirtualBox (https://www.virtualbox.org/), the following steps can be taken to install the VM

Once imported,

The login details are

Username: raven
Password: raven

When opening a terminal it should automatically be using the raven environment and at the correct folder, but if not

```
cd Desktop/RaVeN  
conda activate raven
```

On the desktop, there is a file called Test Commands that allows for easy copying into the terminal for testing.

System requirements

1. **Memory requirement:** We segregate our experiments into two categories - 1) small-scale experiments on smaller networks requiring at least 16 GB RAM and 2) large-scale experiments on larger networks requiring at least 64 GB RAM (RAM can be set in virtual machine manager, i.e. VirtualBox -> RaVeN-VM -> System -> Motherboard -> Base Memory).
2. **Gurobi license:** We provide an academic license to run experiments on the VM; however, if this does not work or if you would like to provide your own license you may request a license from Gurobi and enter the command given in the terminal.

Caveats

The reported runtime can change depending on the hardware used to run these experiments and may not exactly match the runtimes reported in the paper.

Instructions for reproducing experiments

Untargeted UAP verification

Small-scale experiments Instructions [Approximate runtime: ~30 Mins./experiment]

1. Move to the RaVeN directory

```
cd RaVeN
```

2. Run any experiment by replacing ``test_name`` with any test from class ``TestUntargetedUapSmall`` from the file ``RaVeN/src/tests/test_raven.py``

```
python -m unittest -v src.tests.test_raven.TestUntargetedUapSmall.test_name
```

3. Example of an experiment on a single network

```
python -m unittest -v src.tests.test_raven.TestUntargetedUapSmall.test_convsmall_diffai_mnist
```

4. Approximate Runtime ~30 Mins (this is a rough estimate and depends on the hardware)
5. Expected terminal output (example)

For each relational property

```
***** verifying property 2 *****  
  
Individual certified UAP accuracy: 0.00 %  
I/O Formulation certified UAP accuracy: 0.00 %  
RaVeN certified UAP accuracy: 40.00 %  
Improvement over Individual 40.00 %  
Improvement over I/O Formulation 40.00 %
```

Aggregated Result (over 20 relational properties)

```
***** Aggregated Result *****

Individual certified UAP accuracy: 40.00 %
I/O Formulation certified UAP accuracy: 40.00 %
RaVeN certified UAP accuracy: 70.00 %
Improvement over Individual 30.00 %
Improvement over I/O Formulation 30.00 %

***** Aggregated Runtime *****

Avg. Individual time: 0.399 sec.
Avg. I/O Formulation time: 0.466 sec.
Avg. RaVeN time: 13.332 sec.
```

Large-scale experiments Instructions [Approximate runtime: can take several hours]

- 6. Move to the RaVeN directory

```
cd RaVeN
```

- 7. Run any experiment by replacing ``test_name`` with any test from class ``TestUntargetedUapLarge`` from the file ``RaVeN/src/tests/test_raven.py``

```
python -m unittest -v src.tests.test_raven.TestUntargetedUapLarge.test_name
```

- 8. Example of an experiment on a single network

```
python -m unittest -v src.tests.test_raven.TestUntargetedUapLarge.test_convbig_diffai_mnist
```

Worst-case hamming distance verification

Small-scale experiments Instructions [Approximate runtime: ~20 Mins./experiment]

- Move to the RaVeN directory

```
cd RaVeN
```

- Run any experiment by replacing ``test_name`` with any test from class ``TestWorstCaseHamming`` from the file ``RaVeN/src/tests/test_raven.py``

```
python -m unittest -v src.tests.test_raven.TestWorstCaseHamming.test_name
```

- Example of an experiment on a single network

```
python -m unittest -v src.tests.test_raven.TestWorstCaseHamming.test_mnist_hamming_sigmoid
```

- Approximate Runtime ~20 Mins (this is a rough estimate and depends on the hardware)

- Expected terminal output (example)

For each relational property

```
***** verifying property 2 *****  
  
Individual worst-case hamming distance: 11.00  
I/O Formulation worst-case hamming distance: 6.00  
RaVeN worst-case hamming distance: 3.00  
Reduction over Individual 8.00  
Reduction over I/O Formulation 3.00
```

Aggregated Result (over 20 relational properties)

```
***** Aggregated Result *****
```

```
Individual worst-case hamming distance: 10.80
```

```
I/O Formulation worst-case hamming distance: 7.10
```

```
RaVeN worst-case hamming distance: 2.95
```

```
Reduction over Individual 7.85
```

```
Reduction over I/O Formulation 4.15
```

```
***** Aggregated Runtime *****
```

```
Avg. Individual time: 0.076 sec.
```

```
Avg. I/O Formulation time: 0.301 sec.
```

```
Avg. RaVeN time: 6.752 sec.
```

Monotonicity verification

Experiments Instructions [Approximate runtime: <1 Mins./experiment]

- Move to the RaVeN directory

```
cd RaVeN
```

- Run any experiment by replacing ``test_name`` with any test from class ``TestMonotonicity`` from the file ``RaVeN/src/tests/test_raven.py``

```
python -m unittest -v src.tests.test_raven.TestMonotonicity.test_name
```

- Example of an experiment on a single network

```
python -m unittest -v src.tests.test_raven.TestMonotonicity.test_housing_mono
```

- Approximate Runtime <1 Mins (this is a rough estimate and depends on the hardware)
- Expected output

```
***** Feature 0, Eps 50.0 *****  
Verified: 31, Time: 1.068467617034912
```

Targeted UAP verification

Experiments Instructions [Approximate runtime: ~30 Mins./experiment]

- Move to the RaVeN directory

```
cd RaVeN
```

- Run any experiment by replacing ``test_name`` with any test from class ``TestTargetedUap`` from the file ``RaVeN/src/tests/test_raven.py``

```
python -m unittest -v src.tests.test_raven.TestTargetedUap.test_name
```

- Example of an experiment on a single network

```
python -m unittest -v src.tests.test_raven.TestTargetedUap.test_convsmall_diffai_cifar10
```

- Approximate Runtime ~30 Mins (this is a rough estimate and depends on the hardware)

Ablation w.r.t difference constraints

Small-scale experiments Instructions [Approximate runtime: ~30 Mins./experiment]

1. Move to the RaVeN directory

```
cd RaVeN
```

2. Run any experiment by replacing ``test_name`` with any test from class ``TestDifferenceAblation`` from the file ``RaVeN/src/tests/test_raven.py``

```
python -m unittest -v src.tests.test_raven.TestDifferenceAblation.test_name
```

3. Example of an experiment on a single network

```
python -m unittest -v src.tests.test_raven.TestDifferenceAblation.test_mnist_hamming_sigmoid
```

4. Approximate Runtime ~30 Mins (this is a rough estimate and depends on the hardware)
5. Expected terminal output (example)

For each relational property

```
***** verifying property 2 *****  
  
Individual worst-case hamming distance: 16.00  
I/O Formulation worst-case hamming distance: 16.00  
RaVeN no difference constraints worst-case hamming distance: 16.00  
RaVeN worst-case hamming distance: 13.00  
Reduction over Individual 3.00  
Reduction over I/O Formulation 3.00  
Reduction over no difference constraints 3.00
```

Aggregated Result (over 20 relational properties)

```

***** Aggregated Result *****

Individual worst-case hamming distance: 15.15
I/O Formulation worst-case hamming distance: 15.15
RaVeN no difference constraints worst-case hamming distance: 14.75
RaVeN worst-case hamming distance: 11.55
Reduction over Individual 3.60
Reduction over I/O Formulation 3.60
Reduction over no difference constraints 3.20

***** Aggregated Runtime *****

Avg. Individual time: 0.069 sec.
Avg. I/O Formulation time: 0.257 sec.
Avg. RaVeN no difference time: 1.451 sec.
Avg. RaVeN time: 9.247 sec.

```

Designing custom tests

1. Update the parameters in the `test_custom` from `TestRavenCustom` in the file `RaVeN/src/tests/test_raven.py`.
2. The class `RaVeNArgs` from `RaVeN/src/raven_args.py` defines the parameters.
3. After updating parameters Move to the RaVeN directory

```
cd RaVeN
```

4. Run the following command from

```
python -m unittest -v src.tests.test_raven.TestRavenCustom.test_custom
```